

POLYSACCHARIDES AS CARRIERS AND PROTECTORS OF ADDITIVES AND BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS IN FOOD

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Review

Abstract

Polysaccharides based carriers show promising potential in food bioactive ingredients encapsulation, protection, and delivery Due to their combination of featured properties. Among the various natural polymers, polysaccharides are one of the best biopolymers. They play a very crucial role as carriers and protectors of additives and bioactive compounds which are due to the presence of hydroxyl groups which allow for easy preparation of their chemical derivatives. Polysaccharides such as cellulose, starch, chitosan etc. have several industrial applications but due to some distinguished characteristics properties, seaweed polysaccharides are preferred. This review provide concise information on the characteristic of selected polysaccharides, advantages and disadvantages of polysaccharides based edible films and coating, use of polysaccharides based films and coating as carriers of additives and bioactive compounds on food. This review provides concise information of the methodology for film and coating formation, incorporation of bioactive compounds and ways of application.

Keywords: Polysaccharides, seaweed, bioactive, delivery system, edible films and coating

1. INTRODUCTION

Food bioactive are physiologically active components in foods such as vegetables, fruits, and whole grains, which may provide desirable health benefits beyond basic nutrition to reduce the risk of chronic disease and the process of carcinogenesis. The addition of bioactive to foods, particularly those foods that are consumed as part of the normal diet of target populations, offers opportunities for improving the health and well-being of consumers. The delivery of bioactive through food is a major challenge as many bioactive are prone to degradation. There is therefore a need to protect them throughout their shelf life in fortified food products, without compromising the sensory properties of the food.

The overall quality and shelf-life of fresh foods post-harvest or -slaughter is reduced by several factors including microbial growth, water loss, enzymatic browning, lipid oxidation, off flavor, texture deterioration, rise in respiration rate and senescence processes, among others. Fresh cut meat products these events are accelerated due to lesions of tissues during cutting and grounding, also fresh cut vegetables and fruits these events are accelerated due to lesions of tissues during peeling, slicing and cutting. Fresh-cut fruits and vegetables during mechanical operations are exposed to spoil because the natural protection of fruit (the peel or skin) is generally removed and hence, they become highly susceptible to microbial growth due to the leakage of juices and sugar from damaged tissues which allow the growth and fermentation of some microorganism. Likewise, during processing, enzymes such as polyphenol oxidase, polygalacturonase and pectin methyl esterase are released, thus causing, browning

and softening from the tissues, respectively Appearance/color, texture, and flavor are the main quality attributes that affect consumer acceptance of meat, and lipid oxidation is one of the primary causes by quality deterioration in meat and meat products, dairy products such as fresh and semi-hard cheeses are complex food products consisting mainly of casein, fat, and water. Such products are highly perishable due to the high content of moisture (only in fresh cheeses) and microorganisms, and some cases high fat-content. These microbial activities affect are major cause of quality deteriorations.

To solve the effect of microbial activities on fresh cuts fruits, dairy, meat and other food products new technologies have been applied to counteract these negatives effects. Among them, polysaccharide-based edible films and coatings have emerged like good alternative for enhancing the quality and safety of such foods. Edible films and coatings have been used to reduce the deleterious effect caused by minimal processing. Numerous studies show that natural polysaccharides are well suited for use as packaging material for fresh fruit and vegetables and can often be an important alternative to synthetic compounds. Natural polymer materials are a good barrier to oxygen and carbon dioxide; however, they are characterized by excessive solubility in the water environment, water vapor permeability and low extensibility. The use of polysaccharides for the preparation of edible films and coatings is justified not only by the possibility of reducing the consumption of packaging made of synthetic polymer materials but also by the fact that the production of some natural polymers can be made using waste products generated during the processing of food raw materials polysaccharide-based edible films and coatings as polymeric matrix to carrier additive or bioactive compounds such as antimicrobial, antioxidant, antisoftening and nutraceutical for enhancing the shelf-life, safety and sensor attributes of fresh food products, as well as methodologies of forming and application of edible films and coatings and futures trends using microencapsulation or nanotechnology.

2. CHARACTERISTICS OF SELECTED POLYSACCHARIDES

Polysaccharide film are made from starch, alginates, cellulose ethers, chitosan, carrageenan, or pectin's impact hardness, crispness, compactness, thickening quality, viscosity, adhesiveness, and gel forming ability to a variety of films. These films because of the makeup of the polymer chains exhibit excellent gas permeability properties, resulting in desirable modified atmosphere that enhances the shelf life of the products without creating anaerobic conditions.

Seaweed Polysaccharides

Seaweeds are usually found on rocks, pebbles, shells, and seawater plants in shallow waters at a depth of 180 m. It has a rapid growth rate and is highly abundant. Seaweeds are mainly used as food products, fertilizers, animal feed, and medicine. Seaweed consumption has increased by about 176% since 1995. Due to its multifunctional applications, high cost ~USD 50–80/ton, and the trend of being used as sustainability products, seaweed cultivation is currently in demand. However, seaweed cultivation and farming are very limited as they are presently confined to coastal areas (Nakhate et al., 2021).

As mentioned above, the seaweeds are classified into green seaweeds (Chlorophyceae), red seaweeds (Rhodophyceae), and brown seaweeds (Phaeophyceae) depending upon the pigmentation. The green seaweed species *Cladophora*, *Ulva*, and *Monostroma* produce the acidic polysaccharide Ulvan. Red

seaweeds *Poryphyra capensis*, *Aeodes orbitosa*, *Notogenia stiriata* widely produce Agar and Carrageenan. While brown seaweeds *Laminaria pallida*, *Fucus*, and *Zonaria* species produce the polysaccharides Alginate, Fucoidan, and Laminarin. All species of seaweeds have high carbohydrate (accounting for about 40% of the mass) content, while brown seaweed also has a high protein content (Nakhate et al., 2021).

The most commonly used seaweed polysaccharides are Alginate, Agar, and Carrageenan, as shown in Table 1. Alginate consists of D-mannuronic acid and L-guluronic acid (G) in varied molecular weights, proportions, and configurations. The properties of alginate depend upon the ratio of mannuronic acid and guluronic acid. When alginate consists of a higher amount of guluronic acid, there is a high ability to form strong bonds. In contrast, if the guluronic acid levels are low, a softer and more flexible structure is formed. As a result of the chemical structure alginate exhibits unique colloidal properties, these aids in stabilizing and thickening of films or coating. Alginate is used as a coating material because of its propensity to react irreversibly and efficiently with divalent and trivalent metal cations to create water-insoluble polymers. Alginate has good film-forming ability with high transparency and uniformity. Further, it is impermeable to fats and oils. Carrageenan is a hydrophilic polymer consisting of a linear chain of partially sulphated galactans. It is mainly made up of three types: kappa carrageenan, iota carrageenan, and lambda carrageenan. With potassium salts, kappa carrageenan produces strong gels; with calcium salts, it produces brittle gels. Kappa carrageenan coatings efficiently protect vegetables and fruit from moisture loss and oxidation. Agar is formed from a mixture of agarose and agarpectin. Agar is primarily composed of L and D galactose units that are alternated regularly. Agarose is responsible for the gelling properties of agar, making it suitable to form films and coatings. Agar can generate transparent, robust, thermoreversible gels which are water in soluble (Kocira et al., 2021). The biocompatibility, gel-forming ability, emulsification, gelation, and foaming) capabilities of various seaweed polysaccharides are based on their unique structure. In addition to the properties of the seaweed, its nutritional value including minerals, vitamins, calories, and antioxidants, are beneficial in making edible films and coatings.

Table 1. Seaweed polysaccharides commonly used as films and coatings

Seaweed	Polysaccharides	Structure	Reference
Brown seaweed	Alginate		(Carina et al., 2021)
Red seaweed	Agar		(Carina et al., 2021)
	Carrageenan		(Carina et al., 2021)
Green seaweed	Ulvan		(Carina et al., 2021)

Seaweed's non-lethal, non-toxic properties, as well as its film-forming abilities, have led to its use as edible films and coatings. The mechanism for developing these seaweed-based FCMs has been demonstrated in Figure 1

Figure 1.

Figure 1. The mechanism for developing seaweed-based food polysaccharide materials. (a) Mangoes coated in chitosan- and alginates-based coatings enriched with cinnamon essential oil microcapsules (Yin et al., 2019). (b) Active packaging of cold-smoked salmon with Zn-MgO/Alginate film (Vizzini et al., 2020), (c) Some examples of edible films (Nešić et al., 2020), (d) Intelligent packaging of shrimp and duria using t-carrageenan based colorimetric pH sensor film (Ahmad et al., 2019).

3. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF POLYSACCHARIDES BASED EDIBLE FILMS AND COATING

To state the advantages and disadvantages of polysaccharides based edible films we need to sort the type of polysaccharides.

Types of polysaccharides based films

Polysaccharides can be categories based from their sources which are; seaweeds, starch chitin/chitosan and cellulose derivatives.

3.1 Seaweeds polysaccharides: these are polysaccharides derived from seaweed which includes alginates, Agar and carrageenan.

Alginate:

Alginates are derived from seaweed and possess good film-forming properties that make them particularly useful in food application. Alginate has a potential to form biopolymer film or coating component because of its unique colloidal properties, which include thickening, stabilization, suspending, film forming, gel producing, and emulsion stabilizing (Rhim.,2004). Divalent cations (calcium, magnesium, manganese, aluminum or iron) are used as gelling agents in alginate film formation. Desirable properties attributed to alginates films, include moisture retention, reduction in shrinkage improved product texture, juiciness, color, and odor of foods.

Agar:

Agar is a hydrophilic colloid consisting of a mixture of agarose and agaropectin that have the ability to form reversible gels simply by cooling a hot aqueous solution. Used extensively in microbiological media to provide firmness, agar exhibits characteristics that make it useful for coating meats. It forms strong gels characterized by melting points far above the initial gelation temperature (Natrajan & Sheldon, 2000). Agar gel melts on heating and resets on cooling. Because of its ability to form very hard gels at very low concentrations and the simplicity of the extraction process, agar has been used extensively as a gelling agent in the food industry. However, despite its biodegradability and its enormous gelling power, agar has not been used widely due to poor aging. Both photodegradation and fluctuations in ambient temperature and humidity alter agar crystallinity, leading to formation of micro-fractures and polymer embrittlement (Freile-Pelegrin.,2007). The influence of agar on the structure and the functional properties of emulsified edible films has been recently studied by (Phan et al.,2009).

Carrageenan:

carrageenan's are water-soluble polymers with a linear chain of partially sulphated galactans, which present high potentiality as film-forming material. These sulphated polysaccharides are extracted from the cell walls of various red seaweeds (Rhodophyceae). Carrageenan film formation includes a gelation mechanism during moderate drying, leading to a three-dimensional network formed by polysaccharide - double helices and to a solid film after solvent evaporation (Karbowski.,2006) Recently, carrageenan films were also found to be less opaque than those made of starch (Ribeiro.,2007)

3.2 Starch source polysaccharides

Starch composed of amylose and amylopectin, is primarily derived from cereal grains like corn(maize), with the largest source of starch. Other commonly used sources are wheat, potato, tapioca and rice. Amylose is responsible for film-forming capacity of starch (Claudia.,2005). High amylose starch films have been that are flexible, oxygen impermeable, oil resistant, heat sealable, and water soluble .starch based films exhibit physical characteristics similar to plastic films in that they are odorless, colorless, non-toxic, biologically absorbable, semi-permeable to carbon dioxide, and resistant to passage of oxygen. Since the water activity is critical for microbial, chemical, and enzymatic activities, edible starch based films can retard microbial growth by lowering the water activity within the package.

3.3 Cellulose Derivatives:

Cellulose derivatives are polysaccharides composed of linear chains of β (1-4) glucosidic units with methyl, hydroxypropyl or carboxyl substituents. Only four cellulose derivative forms are used for edible coatings or films: Hydroxypropyl cellulose (E463; HPC), hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (E464; HPMC), Carboxymethylcellulose (E466; CMC) or Methyl cellulose (E461; MC). Cellulose derivatives exhibit thermo-gelation. Therefore when suspensions are heated they form a gel whereas they return to their original consistency when cooled (Murray J. C. F,2000). However, cellulose derivative films are poor water vapour barriers because of the inherent hydrophilic nature of polysaccharides and they possess poor mechanical properties.

3.4 Chitin/Chitosan:

Chitosan is an edible and biodegradable polymer derived from chitin, the major organic skeletal substance from crustacean shells. This is the second most abundant natural and non-toxic polymer in nature after cellulose. Some desirable properties of chitosan are that it forms films without the addition of additives, exhibits good oxygen and carbon dioxide permeability, as well as excellent mechanical properties and antimicrobial activity against bacteria, yeasts, and molds (Var Tiainen et al., 2004). However, a major drawback of chitosan is its poor solubility in neutral solutions. The required degree of deacetylation to obtain a soluble product must be 80–85% or higher (Park,2002). Chitosan can form transparent films to enhance the quality and extend the storage life of food products (Ribeiro,2007). Pure chitosan films are generally cohesive, compact and the film surface has a smooth contour without pores or cracks.

3.5 Gums: Gums are usually considered to be non-starch, water-soluble polysaccharides with commercial importance. Gums in edible-film preparation are used for their texturizing capabilities. All gums are polysaccharides composed of sugars other than glucose. Gums are differentiated into three groups (Williams,2000): exudate gums (gum Arabic; mesquite gum), the extractive gums (from endosperm of some legume seeds or extracted from the wood: guar gum) and the microbial fermentation gums (xanthan gum). In edible-forming preparations, guar gum (E 412) is used as a water binder, stabilizer and viscosity builder. Gum Arabic (E 414), owing to its solubility in hot or cold water, is the least viscous of the hydrocolloid gums. Xanthan gum (E 415) is readily dispersed in water; hence high consistency is obtained rapidly in both hot and cold systems. A blend of guar gum, gum Arabic and xanthan gum provided uniform coatings with good cling and improved adhesion in wet batters (Mei.,2002). The mesquite gum forms films with excellent water vapor barrier properties when small amounts of lipids are added in their formulation (Diaz-Sobac.,2002).

Table 2. Shows the advantages and disadvantages of polysaccharide edible films and coatings

NO.	Advantages	Disadvantages	Reference
1	preserve the composition of food products	sometimes the formed edible coating has a thick layer	Hammam et al. 2019
2	EFC can improve the nutritional value of food	some edible film and coatings are hygroscopic in nature, which helps to increase the possible growth of microbes	Radoslav Radev, 2021
3	maintain quality of food products during storage	some of the components of edible films and coatings can cause allergic reactions in consumers	Radoslav Radev, 2021
4	enhance the sensory properties of food	high cost of the components and reduce the economic efficiency	Kamal et al.2019

5	EFC may include in the composition antimicrobial and antioxidant agents	lack of sufficient information for the use of machinery and equipment for the production of edible films and coating	Hammam et al. 2019
6	shelf-life extension and safety enhancement	need for a second packing material because more of edible films and coating have lesser physical and chemical resistance compared to synthetic packaging	Tavassoli-Kafrani et al.2020
7	reduce weight loss and firmness loss	high cost of some physico-mechanical laboratory tests for the properties of edible films and coating	Kapetanakou et al.2014

The results of Table 2 show that the advantages of edible films and coatings supersede their disadvantages. The advantages of edible coatings have shown credible impact to food, vegetable and fruits. Edible films and coating provide significant advantage on the quality food as it serve as a means that ;preserve the composition of food products, Edible films and coating can improve the nutritional value of food maintain quality of food products during storage, enhance the sensory properties of food, edible films and coating can contain health beneficial nutrients, advantages of using edible films and coating about shelf-life extension and safety enhancement, edible films and coating may include in the composition antimicrobial and antioxidant agents, shelf-life extension and safety enhancement. Edible films and coating have good barrier properties. The disadvantages of edible films and coatings include; some edible film and coatings are hygroscopic in nature; which helps to increase the possible growth of microbes, some of the components of edible films and coatings can cause allergic reactions in consumers, about the production and applying of edible films and coating sometimes the formed edible coating has a thick layer, there are difficulties in applying edible films and coatings on the surface of food products; disadvantages about the price and the economic efficiency about application of edible films and coating, High cost of the components and reduce the economic efficiency.

The summarized results of the advantages and disadvantages of edible films and coatings are important for the development of research on edible films and coating. The advantages of edible films and coating that authors should use and deepen their work are regarding the fact that: Edible films and coating preserve food quality; Edible films and coating extend the shelf life of food; the use of edible films and coating may limit the use of synthetic packaging; in the production of edible films and coating, they have good physico-mechanical and barrier properties. The disadvantage of the edible films and coating about that the scientific community must work on is to create appropriate strategies, opportunities and conditions to minimize the negative effects about: the composition of the edible films and coating; the production and application of edible films and coating; the price and the economic efficiency about the application of edible films and coating; the regulatory requirements of the edible films and coating.

4. USES OF POLYSACCHARIDES BASED EDIBLE FILMS AND COATING AS CARRIERS OF ADITIVES AND BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS ON FOOD

The overall quality of food products decreases from harvest or slaughter until they are consumed. Quality loss may be due to microbiological, enzymatic, chemical, or physical changes. Therefore, food additives should be added to prevent the quality loss and extend the shelf-life of foods. The use of films and

coatings have been a good alternative for carrier different additives and bioactive compounds to the food, as well as, to protect them of the water loss, volatile compounds loss, discoloration, gas permeability and microbial spoilage; since, these can to guarantee the controlled supply of antimicrobial, antioxidant and nutraceutical compounds.

Components of Film Additives

- Antimicrobial compounds
- Antioxidants
- Flavor and aroma compounds
- Pigments
- Preservatives
- Vitamins

Types of Film Additives

- Emulsifiers keep the components in solution.
- Surfactants reduce the surface tension of the film formulation to achieve uniform coverage. Surfactants may be used to stabilize the dispersed phase in a polymeric solution prior to applying it to food surface.
- Plasticizers:

Plasticizers are used to modify mechanical properties of films and coatings

Plasticizers, which are small molecules such as glycerol, propylene glycol, or polyethylene glycol are used to control viscosity of the liquid formulation, add flexibility and tensile strength and control surface tension.

Carriers of antimicrobial compounds

Antimicrobial agents: incorporating antimicrobial compounds into edible films or coatings provides a novel way to improve the food safety and shelf life of ready-to-eat foods.

Common antimicrobial agents used in food systems, such as benzoic acid, sodium benzoate, sorbic acid, potassium sorbate, and propionic acid, may be incorporated into edible films and coatings. Example:

- Starch based coating containing potassium sorbate were applied on the surface of fresh strawberries for reducing microbial growth and extending storage life.
- Chitosan coatings containing potassium sorbate were shown to increase antifungal activity against the growth of *Cladosporium* and *Rhizopus* on fresh strawberries.

Antioxidants and antibrowning agents:

Antioxidants can be added into coating matrix to protect against oxidative rancidity, degradation and discoloration of certain foods. E.g. nuts were coated with pectinate, pectate, and zein coatings containing BHA, BHT, and citric acid to prevent rancidity and maintain their texture.

Ascorbic acid was incorporated into edible coatings to reduce enzymatic browning in sliced apples and potatoes. The polysaccharides of the green seaweed (*Ulva lactuca*), the red seaweeds (*Gracilaria lemaneiformis* and *Sarcodia ceylonensis*), and the brown algae (*Durvillaea antarctica*) were extracted through microwave- assisted extraction. The antioxidant activity was then measured through an ABTS radical scavenging activity assay (DPPH), the scavenging activities of hydroxyl radical, nitrite scavenging activity and the determination of the reducing power. The results of the DPPH showed that the polysaccharide from the green seaweed showed the highest activity while the polysaccharide extracted

from the brown seaweed and from *Sarcodia ceylonensis* also showed a noticeable effect on the DPPH. The *Gracilaria lemaneiformis* showed only weak antioxidant activities as it is a non-sulphated polysaccharide. The *Sarcodia ceylonensis* and green seaweed polysaccharide showed high hydroxyl radical scavenging activity, while the brown seaweed polysaccharide had a more pronounced reducing power (He et al., 2016). Kanatt et al. (2020) determined the antioxidant activity of aqueous seaweed Nutrients, flavours and colorants:

extracts from *Kappaphycus alvarezii* with a DPPH assay, the iron chelation activity, a β -carotene bleaching assay and a reducing power assay (Kanatt et al., 2020).

Overall, the results showed that most polysaccharides exhibit antioxidant activity to varying degrees, these properties can be used in antioxidant packaging. However, to enhance the antioxidant properties components like plant essential oils, mulberry extract etc. can be added to guarantee the reduction of lipid oxidation and increase the safety of the food. Additionally, the antioxidant activity of different seaweed polysaccharides/extracts should be further investigated to reach the full potential of seaweed as an antioxidant agent in active food packaging.

Edible films and coatings are excellent vehicles to enhance the nutritional value of fruits and vegetables by delivering basic nutrients and nutraceuticals that are lacking or are present on only low quantity. Xanthan gum coating was utilized to carry a high concentration of calcium and vitamin E, for not only preventing moisture loss and surface whitening, but also to significantly increase the calcium and vitamin E contents of the carrots. In general, fruits, vegetables and seafood industries could apply different polysaccharides based coatings (alginate, gellan, chitosan and gum) as excellent carriers of nutraceutical compounds for adding nutritive value and functional properties to the products. In general, fruits, vegetables and seafood industries could apply different polysaccharides based coatings (alginate, gellan, chitosan and gum) as excellent carriers of nutraceutical compounds for adding nutritive value and functional properties to the products

Classification of some antimicrobial, antioxidant agents and additives allowed for used in food coatings

Food additives	Classification	Recognized by	Reference
Benzoic acid	Preservatives	Generally recognized as safe (GRAS)	Kalpana et al., 2019
Cloves bud oil	Essential oil	Generally recognized as safe (GRAS)	Kapadiya et al., 2016
Potassium sorbate	Preservative	Generally recognized as safe (GRAS)	Monya et al., 2021
Propionic acid	Preservative	Generally recognized as safe (GRAS)/FDA	Bankole et al., 2020

Calcium chloride	Antimicrobial agent	Generally recognized as safe (GRAS)/FDA	Bingyu et al., 2022
Ascorbic acid	Antioxidant, preservative, colour stabilizer, nutrient	Generally recognized as safe (GRAS)	Jack Rowland, 2018
Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT)	Antioxidant	Generally recognized as safe (GRAS)	Aronson et al., 2016
Butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA)	Antioxidant	Generally recognized as safe (GRAS)/FS	Kashyap et al., 2005

Edible coatings have been successfully applied in processed foods such as meat, cereals, confectionaries, dried fruits, nuts and fresh and fresh-cut fruits and vegetables. These coating improves the quality and shelf life of foods. These films acts as a novel packaging systems and control the release of active compounds such as antioxidants, flavours, and antimicrobial agents.

Figure 3.

Figure 3. shows the bilateral protein films (New Gem) used to coat fresh meat products. Antimicrobial or antioxidant compounds incorporated into the polymer matrix may prevent growth of spoilage and pathogenic

microorganisms, delay of meat fat rancidity, discoloration prevention, and even improvement of the nutritional quality of coated food.

Figure 4.

Figure 4. shows Confectionery coatings also known as candy wafers or compound coating which is easy to use substitute for real chocolate. Confectionery coating uses a vegetable fat to replace the cocoa butter that is found in genuine chocolate by substituting the cocoa butter, confectionery coating do not need to be tempered (heated and cooled in a precise fashion).

5. METHODOLOGY FOR FILM AND COATING FORMATION, INCORPORATION OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS AND WAYS OF APPLICATIONS

Film and coating formation, and incorporation of additives/bioactive compounds

An edible film is essentially an interacting polymer network of three-dimensional gel structure. Despite the film-forming process, whether it is wet casting or dry casting, film forming materials should form a spatially rearranged gel structure with all incorporated film-forming agents, such as biopolymers, plasticizers, other additives, and solvents in the case of wet casting. Biopolymers film-forming materials are generally gelatinized to produce film-forming solutions. Sometimes drying of the hydrogels is necessary to eliminate excess solvents from the gel structure. This does not mean that the film-forming mechanism during the drying process is only the extension of the wet-gelation mechanism. The film-forming mechanism during the drying process may differ from the wet-gelation mechanism, though wet gelation is initial stage of the film-forming process. There could be a critical stage of a transition from a wet gel to a dry film, which relates to a phase transition from a polymer-in-water (or other solvents) system to a water-in-polymer system.

Two processes can be used for film-production: dry and wet. The dry process of edible film production does not use liquid solvent, such as water or alcohol. Molten casting, extrusion, and heat pressing are good examples of dry process. For the dry process, heat is applied to the film-forming materials to increase the

temperature to above the melting point of the film-forming materials, to cause them to flow. The wet process uses solvents for the dispersion of film-forming materials, followed by drying to remove the solvent and form a film structure. For the wet process the selection of solvents is the one of the most important factors. Since the film-forming solution should be edible and biodegradable, only water, ethanol and their mixtures are appropriated as solvents. To produce a homogeneous film structure avoiding phase separation, various emulsifiers can be added to the film forming solution. This solvent compatibility of ingredients is very important to develop homogeneous edible film and coating systems carrying active agents.

Ways of application of films and coatings

There are several for applying films and coating which include;

- I. Dipping
- II. Dripping
- III. Foaming
- IV. Fluidized-bed coating
- V. Panning
- VI. Spraying
- VII. Electrostatic coating

The selection of an appropriate method depends on the characteristics of the food, the coating materials, the intended effect of the coating, and the cost.

- I. Dipping: edible coatings can be applied by dipping products in coating solutions and then allowing excess coating to drain as it dries and solidifies. Dipping has been commonly used for coating fruits, vegetables, and meat products. The first reported dipping application was by the Florida citrus industry, where the fruits were submerged into a tank of emulsion coating. Fruit was then generally conveyed to a drier under ambient condition.

Figure 5.

Figure 5; The figure above shows the concept of dipping technique which is by immersing the fresh food produce into coating solution to allow complete wetting of the surface of the material. After the coating solution is drained out to remove excess coating from the food surface.

- II. **Dripping:** This coating application method is the most economic. In addition, it has the ability to deliver the coating either directly to the commodity surface or to the brushes. However, due to relatively large droplet sizes, good uniform coverage can only be achieved when the commodity has adequate tumbling action over several brushes that are saturated with the coatings. Dripping has been commonly used for coating fruits and vegetables.

- III. **FOAMING:** foam application is used for some emulsion coatings. A foaming agent is added to the coating or compressed air is blown into the applicator tank. Extensive tumbling action is necessary to break the foam for uniform distribution. The agitated foam is applied to commodities moving by on rollers and cloth flaps or brushes the distribute the emulsion over the surface of the commodity. This type of emulsion contains little water and therefore dries quickly, but inadequate coverage is often a problem.

- IV. **FLUIDIZED-BED COATING:** is a technique that can be used to apply a very thin layer onto dry particles of very low density or small size. It was originally developed as a pharmaceutical coating techniques but is now increasingly being applied in the food industry It may be applied to enhance the effect of functional ingredients and additives such as processing aids, preservatives, fortifiers,flavours and other additives for ease of handling, improved asthetics, taste and colour. Bakery products are commonly coated using fluidized-bed techniques.

Figure 6.

Figure 6; shows the fluidized bed coating which follows a specific pattern of coating, first the food produce or fresh fruit is sprayed, the sprayed coating act as a layer which covers the whole food produce which is then allowed to dry up after drying the coated product forms a thick fluidized layer.

- V. **PANNING:** panning is usually employed for coating candies ,nuts, and some processed fruits that are characterized by a smooth, regular surface obtained by polishing action in the pan. The technology involves a stainless steel pan that is enclosed and perforated along the side panels. The coating is delivered by a pump to spray guns mounted in various parts of the pan. Panning is a slow process, in which the pan speeds vary based on the size of the centre. For ex- large size nuts require speeds of 15rpm.

Figure 7.

Figure 7; shows the chocolate panning process that uses a panning chocolate machine with rotating drums to cover inclusions with a fat-based coating which does not limit the option to chocolate. Covering can also include everything from dark chocolate to yogurt and nut butters.

- VI. **SPRAYING:** when a thin and uniform coating is required for certain surfaces, spraying is useful. This the most popular method for coating whole fruits and vegetables, especially with the development of high-pressure spray applicators and air- atomizing systems. Spray applications are also suitable when applying films to a particular side or when a dual application must be used for cross-linking, as is practised with alginate coating.

- VII. **ELECTROSTATIC COATING:** is a process that employs charged particles to improve efficiently coat a surface. Powdered particle or atomized liquid is initially projected towards a conductive surface using formal spraying methods and then accelerated toward the surface by a powerful electrostatic charge. The exact performance of liquid electrostatic coating systems for food applications is not well known. These coating shown great promises in some applications, including the impregnation of bread with edible vegetable oil and coating of confectionary and chocolate products.

Figure 8.

Figure 8; shows the process that employs charged particles to more efficient paint a work piece, the work piece which are the fruits or food products are sprayed with electrostatically charged paint particles.

The success of an edible coating for meeting the specific needs of food strongly depends on

- Its barrier property to gases, especially oxygen and water vapor
- Its adhesion to the surface
- Uniformity of coverage of coating and also
- Sensory quality of the coated food products

Conclusions and perspectives

Polysaccharides used as carriers and protectors of additives and bioactive compounds in food have shown very good results on enhancing overall quality, browning, oxidation and softening, shelf-life extension, control of decay, and nutraceutical benefits with a number of diverse additives and bioactive compounds incorporated into edible films and coatings designed for different foods, could be useful to consider that the use of the edible films and coating as carrier of food additives and bioactive compounds represent a good alternative for food industry to improve the quality and safety of the food, as well as to offer new products to consumers. Numerous studies show that natural polysaccharides are well suited for use as packaging material in fresh fruit and vegetables and can often be an important alternative to synthetic compounds. Natural polymer materials are a good barrier to oxygen and carbon dioxide; however, they are characterized by excessive solubility in the water environment, water vapour permeability and low extensibility. Therefore, edible films and coatings derived from polysaccharides should be modified. Replacing synthetic films with edible or biodegradable coatings is desirable from an environmental point of view. Many companies and research institutes are looking for new ingredients with possible health benefits. Ingredients such as phytochemicals, wood-derived ingredients such as phytosterols, pro- and prebiotics, new types of carotenoids, trace minerals and polyphenols will be available in the next years.

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